
NASA Lunabotics: Drivetrain

Model Report
03/14/2025

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Intended Audience

The purpose of this document is to provide a structured and organized report of models for the Drivetrain subsystem for NASA Lunabotics team's robot. This includes use case, data flow, class, and statechart models for the Drivetrain. This document is intended to be used by ERAU's NASA Lunabotics Team.

1.2 Project Overview

NASA Lunabotics is a competition that challenges teams of university students to design, build, and operate a robotic system in moon-like environment. The teams are tasked to have a robot that is able to navigate through the arena from the starting zone down to the mining zone, mine regolith-simulant, and build a berm in a designated construction zone.

The focus of this document will be the Drivetrain subsystem of the robot that the ERAU's team will be designing for the competition. The drivetrain will be a wheel-based design with a steering mechanism(s) to ensure efficient movement.

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2. Use Case Model

The following section contains a description of the actors, use cases, and scenarios in the Drivetrain. Additionally, this section contains a use case diagram that illustrates the relationships between actors and use cases.

2.1 Actors

Below are the actors associated with Drivetrain along with a description:

- **NaviComputer:** a navigation computer that uses sensors from throughout all of subsystems of the robot to come up with various movement commands autonomously.
- **Driver:** a human that can overtake the controls of the robot from the NaviComputer if needed in case of autonomy issues or failure.
- **Power Source:** an electrical subsystem that distributes and manages the power to all subsystems of the robot

2.2 Use Cases

Below are the use cases associated with Drivetrain along with a description:

- **Manage Drivetrain Autonomy:** The Manage Drivetrain Autonomy use case enables the Driver to disengage the autonomy mode. This allows the driver to provide further movement commands to the Drivetrain.
- **Interpret Commands:** The Interpret Commands use case handles the processing of commands that originate from the NaviComputer or the Driver. This includes determining if the motion needed is translation or rotation, what mode of rotation the robot is set for, and determine what actuators need to be powered
- **Monitor Actuators:** The Monitor Actuators use case allows all actors to determine the state of all of Drivetrain’s actuators. This allows for better navigation predictions from NaviComputer, better understanding of power draws and needs for Power Source and provides data for future analysis to the Driver.
- **Set Rotation Mode:** The Set Rotation Mode use case allows the driver to change the rotation mode from swerve steering to differential steering. This would affect which actuators get activated in the Drivetrain.
- **Drive Forward/Backwards:** The Drive Forward/Backwards use case handles determining the power levels needed to be provided to which actuators to achieve the commands from Interpret Commands use case. The use case only deals with translational motion.
- **Rotate Robot:** The Rotate Robot use case handles determining the power levels needed to be provided to which actuators to achieve the commands from Interpret Commands use case. The use case only deals with rotation and heading of the robot.
- **Engage Actuators:** The Engage Actuators allows the Power Source to provide the correct power levels to correct actuators. This use case is an integral part of both Drive Forward/Backwards and Rotate robot use cases.

2.3 Use Case Diagram

The Use Case Diagram is a visual representation of the relationships between different actors and the system itself. It illustrates the primary functions or use cases that the system can perform. The notation used in the diagram is as follows:

- **Actor:** Shown as stick figures, actors are entities that interact with the system. They can be human users or external systems.
- **Use Case:** Shown as ovals, use cases depict specific functionalities or features that the system provides. They are actions that the system can perform.

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- **Associations:** Shown as solid lines connecting actors to use cases, associations show the interaction between actors and the use cases they are involved with.
- **Include Associations:** Shown as a dashed arrow pointing towards the included use case, include associations indicating that one use case includes another use case. The included use case is always performed when the base use case is executed.
- **Extend Associations:** Shown as a dashed arrow pointing from the extended use case, extend associations indicate optional behavior that can extend the base use case.
- **System Boundary:** This is the rectangle that surrounds all the use cases, representing the system's boundaries.

2.4 Scenarios

Below are scenarios for each of the use cases identified in the Drivetrain use case model

Scenario 1: Manage Drivetrain Autonomy

Description: The Driver switching the Drivetrain's autonomy mode.

Actors: Drive, NaviComputer

Precondition: The NaviComputer is doing an insufficient job at giving commands and the Driver is unsatisfied with the system's performance. The autonomy is engaged.

Trigger Condition: The Driver decides to disengage autonomy.

Steps:

- 1- The Driver enters the disengage autonomy command into the system.
- 2- The system stops all of its actuators
- 3- The NaviComputer stops sending commands to the system.
- 4- The system waits for Driver commands. (ALT 1)
- 5- End of use case.

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ALT 1:

Step 4: the Driver decides to also switch rotation modes

4.1: Extend to <<Set Rotation Mode>>

4.2: End of use case.

Scenario 2: Interpret Commands (NaviComputer)

Description: The NaviComputer is sending commands to the system regarding where to go.

Actors: NaviComputer

Precondition: The autonomy is engaged.

Trigger Condition: The NaviComputer has a command ready.

Steps:

1- The NaviComputer sends the command to the system.

2- The system decides to not move or rotate. (ALT 1, ALT 2)

3- End of use case.

ALT 1:

Step 2: the system decides to move forward or backwards

2.1: Extend to <<Drive Forward/Backwards>>

2.2: End of use case.

ALT 1:

Step 2: the system decides to rotate the robot

2.1: Extend to <<Rotate Robot>>

2.2: End of use case.

Scenario 3: Interpret Commands (Driver)

Description: The Driver is sending commands to the system regarding where to go. The default motion is forward.

Actors: Driver

Precondition: The autonomy is disengaged.

Trigger Condition: The driver has a command ready.

Steps:

1- The Drivetrain sends the command to the system.

2- The system decides to move forward/backwards. (ALT 1)

3- Extend to <<Drive Forward/Backwards>>

4- End of use case.

ALT 1:

Step 2: the system is set to rotation control instead of forward/backwards

2.1: Extend to <<Rotate Robot>>

2.2: End of use case.

Scenario 4: Drive Forward/Backwards

Description: The system determined that actuators that create translation are to be used

Actors: None - it is called by internal process

Precondition: The Interpret Command identified translation actuators to be used

Trigger Condition: The Interpret Command sends a request to move forward

Steps:

1- The system receives a request to move forward.

2- Include <<Engage Actuators>> (ALT 1)

3- End of use case.

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ALT 1:

Step 2: the system is also receiving rotation command

2.1: End of use case.

Scenario 5: Rotate Robot

Description: The system determined that actuators that create rotation are to be used. Default rotation mode is Swerve.

Actors: None - it is called by internal process

Precondition: The Interpret Command identified translation actuators to be used

Trigger Condition: The Interpret Command sends a request to rotate the robot

Steps:

- 1- The system receives a request to rotate the robot. (ALT 1)
- 2- The system identifies rotation actuators.
- 3- Include <<Engage Actuators>> (ALT 2)
- 4- End of use case.

ALT 1:

Step 1: the system is also receiving translation commands

1.1: The system blocks Drive Forward/Backwards to be used through the end of this use case.

1.2: The system identifies rotation actuators.

1.3: Include <<Engage Actuators>> (ALT 2)

1.4: End of use case.

ALT 2:

Step 3: the system's rotation mode was changed to Differential.

3.1: The system identifies translation actuators.

3.2: Include <<Engage Actuators>>

3.3: End of use case.

Scenario 6: Engage Actuators (Rotate)

Description: The system determines the power level for specific actuators to rotate the robot.

Actors: Power System

Precondition: Rotation was determined

Trigger Condition: The Interpret Command sends a request to rotate the robot

Steps:

- 1- The system receives a request to rotate the robot.
- 2- The system determines power levels for requested actuators.
- 3- The Power System reads the requested power levels for requested actuators.
- 4- The Power System outputs requested power levels.
- 5- End of use case.

Scenario 7: Set Rotation Mode

Description: The Driver changes the mode of rotation of the robot

Actors: Driver

Precondition: Swerve Steering was deemed unsatisfactory by the Driver

Trigger Condition: The Driver decided to switch rotation modes

Steps:

- 1- The Driver sends a command to switch rotation mode
- 2- The system switched the mode to Differential Steering.

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3- End of use case.

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3. Data Flow Model

The following section describes the data flow model for Drivetrain. The data flow model illustrates how data flows within the system, between sources, sinks, processes, and data stores. It provides a comprehensive understanding of the flow of information through the Drivetrain.

3.1 Data Sources

Below are the data sources present in the Data Flow Model of Drivetrain; they are modeled on the left side of the Data Flow Diagram in Section 3.4:

- **NaviComputer** - a navigation computer that uses the sensors from throughout all of subsystems of the robot to come up with various movement commands autonomously. Generates autonomous movement commands or directions
- **Driver** - a human that can overtake the controls of the robot from the NaviComputer if needed in case of autonomy issues or failure. Generates movement commands, can turn off the autonomy, and toggle rotation and its mode

3.2 Data Sinks

Below are the data sinks present in the Data Flow Model of Drivetrain; they are modeled on the right side of the Data Flow Diagram in Section 3.4:

- **NaviComputer** - the same subsystem as discussed in Section 3.1; it accepts actuator status and related actuatorID
- **Power System** - an electrical subsystem that distributes and manages the power to all subsystems of the robot. It accepts power requests and related actuatorID

3.3 Data Dictionary

Below are the short descriptions of all the data types present in the Data Flow Model of Drivetrain:

Data Name	Generated By	Used By	Description
Actuator Status	P3.3, P1.1	P1.2, P3.4, NaviComputer	Current position or rpm and power draw of the actuator
ActuatorID	P3.3, P1.1	P1.2, P3.4, NaviComputer, Power Source	A unique number associated with a specific actuator
Autonomy Request	Driver	P2	A request to turn off the autonomy
Rotation Mode	Driver	P3.1	A request to switch steering/rotation to Differential
Rotation Toggle	Driver	P3.2	A signal that shows if the joystick values are for rotation or translation
Joystick State	Driver	P3.3	Current position of the joystick that the Driver is using to operate the whole robot.
Autonomy Status	P2	P3.2, P1.1	A variable that tells if autonomy is currently engaged or not

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Power Level Request	P1.2, P3.4	Power System	A request to provide power and its level to a specific actuator; inherently ties with ActuatorID
Movement Directions	NaviComputer	P1.1	Directions and commands from the NaviComputer as to where the NaviComputer wants the robot to go
Updated Rotation Mode	P3.1	P3.3	The processed rotation mode that depends on if the request was made or not to switch.

3.4 Data Flow Diagram

Data Flow Diagram (DFD) is a visual representation of the Data Flow Model. In this section, Level 1 DFD is presented.

3.4.1 Context Diagram

Context Diagram is a simplified visual representation of the Data Flow Model that focuses only on sources, sinks, and data that goes into and out of the system.

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3.4.2 Level 2 Diagrams

In this section, Level 2 diagrams will be shown for processes P1 and P3.

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4. Class Model

The following section describes the class model for Drivetrain. The class model illustrates the system's architecture, identifying the main classes and their relationships.

4.1 Classes

- **Drivetrain** - the system being investigated itself
- **Steering Mechanism** – the mechanism that causes the rotation/steering of the robot
- **Movement Mechanism** - the mechanism that causes the forward and backward translation of the robot
- **Steering Actuator** – an actuator that aids in creating the rotation/steering
- **Movement Actuator** - an actuator that aids in creating the translation
- **Actuator** – a generic class that provides general information about all actuators
- **Wheel** – a component that aids in all motion of the robot
- **Actuator Sensor** – a sensor that is able to collect information about an actuator
- **Actuator Controller** – a device that is able to interpret actuator sensor data and able to output commands

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4.2 Class Model

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5. Statechart Model

This section is dedicated to documenting the Statechart Model developed for Drivetrain. The Statechart Model is an essential component of system design, illustrating the various states the system exists in, transitions between these states, and the events triggering these transitions. The Statechart provides a visual representation of Drivetrain’s behavior and helps in understanding, analyzing, and implementing the dynamic aspects of the system’s functionality.

5.1 States

This section provides an overview of the states within Drivetrain. These states represent the progression of behavior the application exhibits in reaction to events. Below is a description of each of the identified states in the system:

- **Monitoring System (Auto):** Initial state when the robot turns on. Autonomy is engaged, and the Drivetrain waits for commands from NaviComputer or override command from Driver
- **Moving (Auto):** State when the robot moves autonomously forward or backwards. It monitors and processes navigation directions and sensor data continuously, and powers translation/movement actuators.
- **Rotating (Auto):** State when the robot rotates/steers autonomously. It monitors and processes navigation directions continuously, and powers rotation/steering actuators.
- **Monitoring System (Auto):** State when the autonomy gets disengaged. The Drivetrain waits for commands from the Driver.
- **Moving (Manual):** State when the robot moves forward or backwards based on manual Driver inputs. It monitors and processes joystick directions and sensor data continuously, and powers translation/movement actuators.
- **Rotating (Manual - Swerve):** State when the robot steers/rotates based on manual Driver inputs. Rotation happens by swerving the wheels, utilizing the steering mechanism. It monitors and processes joystick directions and sensor data continuously, and powers rotation actuators.
- **Rotating (Manual - Differential):** State when the robot steers/rotates based on manual Driver inputs. Rotation happens by locking the wheels in default orientation and uses differential steering, utilizing the movement mechanism and disengaging the rotation mechanism. It monitors and processes joystick directions and sensor data continuously, and powers movement actuators.

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